

The Role of the Odorant Binding Proteins for Insect Repellents: *Docking Studies of Agents that Interfere with Olfaction.*

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1. Case study 2 (SM3)

SM3_A) 50 repellent chemicals with olfactory response in six different types sensilla from *Cx. Quinquefasciatus*.

Liu F, Chen L, Appel AG, & Liu N (2013) Olfactory responses of the antennal trichoid sensilla to chemical repellents in the mosquito, *Culex quinquefasciatus*. *J. Insect Physiol.* 59(11):1169-1177.

<p>Dimethyl phthalate</p>		
<p>Trans-cinnamaldehyde</p>		
<p>R-(+)-Limonene</p>		
<p>Myrcene</p>		
<p>(-)-α-Pinene</p>		

<p>1S-(+)-3-Carene</p>		
<p>Menthoglycol (PMD)</p>		
<p>S-(-)-Perillaldehyde</p>		
<p>(+)-Menthone</p>		
<p>(+)-Terpinen-4-ol</p>		
<p>Menthol</p>		
<p>Linalyl acetate</p>		

<p>Terpinolene</p>		
<p>S-cis-Verbenol</p>		
<p>β-Caryophyllene</p>		
<p>DEET</p>		
<p>Naphthalene</p>		

2. Case study 3 (SM5)

SM5_A) 71 carboxamides derivatives, characterized by a minimum effective dosage (MED, $\mu\text{mol}/\text{cm}^2$)

to the *Aedes aegypti*.

Oliferenko PV, et al. (2013) Promising *Aedes aegypti* Repellent Chemotypes Identified through Integrated QSAR, Virtual Screening, Synthesis, and Bioassay. PLoS ONE 8(9):e64547.

Table SM5_A1. Prediction model and statistical parameters.

Variable	Coefficients					
	Beta	Std.Err.	B	Std.Err.	t(54)	p-level
Intercept			-3.69041	0.660004	-5.59149	0.000001
2GVS	-1.44754	0.185206	-2.40069	0.307157	-7.81583	0.000000
3F1Q	0.28597	0.078342	0.26743	0.073263	3.65021	0.000592
3R10	0.29585	0.141103	0.28379	0.135351	2.09671	0.040718
1QWV	0.60031	0.208731	0.88401	0.307373	2.87600	0.005754
3KIE	0.35319	0.130325	0.34558	0.127517	2.71005	0.008998
1OW4	-0.45112	0.168500	-0.43205	0.161379	-2.67724	0.009811

Regression summary for dependent variable Log(MED): R= 0.86366591; R²= 0.74591880; Adjusted

R²= 0.71768755; F(6,54) = 26.422; $p < 0.00000$; Std. Error of estimate: 0.41570.

Table SM5_A2. Log(MED) observed and obtained values in the QSAR study for the training set.

ID	Case	Observed	Predicted	Residual	Std.Err.	Deleted
001	N-butyl-N-methyl-hexanamide	-0.93181	-1.00777	0.07596	0.093426	0.08000
002	N-butyl-N-ethylhexanamide	-0.80688	-0.86185	0.05498	0.090734	0.05773
003	N,N-diallylhexanamide	-0.70997	-0.79276	0.08280	0.110015	0.08904
004	N-butyl-N-ethyl-2-methylpentanamide	-0.98297	-1.06681	0.08384	0.139270	0.09444
005	N-butyl-N,2-diethylbutanamide	-0.90309	-0.86907	-0.03402	0.137572	-0.03821
007	N-butyl-N-ethyl-3-methylbutanamide	-0.90309	-0.95666	0.05357	0.150081	0.06160
008	N,N-diisobutyl-3-methylbutanamide	-0.39147	-0.46976	0.07829	0.144111	0.08898
009	N-butyl-N-ethyl-2,2-dimethylpropanamide	-0.54363	-0.47051	-0.07313	0.082407	-0.07612
011	1-(1-azepanyl)-2,2-dimethyl-1-propanone	-0.50446	-1.30626	0.80181	0.175251	0.97512
012	(E)-N-butyl-N-ethyl-2-methyl-2-pentenamide	-0.93181	-0.29711	-0.63470	0.093077	-0.66820
013	(E)-N-ethyl-2-methyl-N-(2-methyl-2-propenyl)-2-pentenamide	-0.73993	0.01798	-0.75791	0.101622	-0.80608
014	(E)-2-methyl-N,N-di-2-propenyl-2-pentenamide	-0.37986	-0.91093	0.53107	0.091234	0.55794
015	N-butyl-N-ethyl-3-methyl-2-butenamide	-0.71670	-0.40596	-0.31074	0.116821	-0.33739
016	N-ethyl-3-methyl-N-(2-methyl-2-propenyl)-2-butenamide	-0.50446	-0.93458	0.43012	0.099407	0.45621
017	N,N-diisobutyl-3-methylcrotonamide	-0.65956	-0.24582	-0.41374	0.138629	-0.46551
018	(E)-N-n-butyl-N-ethyl-2-hexenamide	-0.56225	-0.72881	0.16656	0.126738	0.18363
019	(E)-N-cyclohexyl-N-ethyl-2-hexenamide	-0.18642	-0.22266	0.03624	0.131841	0.04030
020	N-butyl-N-methyl-5-hexynamide	-0.73993	-0.99702	0.25710	0.102487	0.27373
021	(E)-N,2-dimethyl-N-octylpent-2-enamide	-0.90309	-0.47958	-0.42351	0.124408	-0.46517
022	N-cyclohexyl-N-ethylhexanamide	-0.57512	-0.19708	-0.37804	0.110575	-0.40682
023	(E)-N,N-di-(2-methylpropyl)-2-hexenamide	-0.20412	0.02993	-0.23405	0.143254	-0.26559
024	N-ethyl-N-phenylhexanamide	-0.20412	0.07515	-0.27927	0.211306	-0.37657
025	N-cyclohexyl-N-ethyl-3-methylbutanamide	-0.76447	-1.23178	0.46731	0.116106	0.50685
026	N-butyl-N-ethyl-2-methylbenzamide	-0.80688	-0.11832	-0.68856	0.118241	-0.74917
027	N-ethyl-2-methyl-N-(2-methyl-2-propenyl)benzamide	-0.83863	-0.71187	-0.12676	0.073039	-0.13080
028	N-ethyl-2-methyl-N-phenylbenzamide	0.71265	0.71524	-0.00259	0.238598	-0.00387
029	N-cyclohexyl-N-methylheptanamide	-0.76447	-0.46033	-0.30415	0.139101	-0.34250
030	(E)-N-cyclohexyl-N-ethyl-2-methylpent-2-enamide	-0.85387	-0.59750	-0.25637	0.194033	-0.32778
032	1-(1-azepanyl)-2-methyl-1-pentanone	-0.99140	-0.48608	-0.50532	0.140060	-0.57003
033	(E)-1-(1-azepanyl)-2-methyl-2-penten-1-one	-1.00877	-0.38411	-0.62466	0.087787	-0.65382
034	hexahydro-1-(3-methylcrotonoyl)-1H-azepine	-0.85387	-0.68149	-0.17238	0.131991	-0.19170
036	N,N-bis(2-methylpropyl)-3-phenyl-2-propenamamide	1.30374	0.54240	0.76134	0.140711	0.85986
037	N-ethyl-N,3-diphenyl-2-propenamamide	1.30643	0.82499	0.48143	0.155848	0.56017
038	N,3-dicyclohexyl-N-ethylpropanamide	1.31175	0.66599	0.64577	0.173455	0.78190
040	4-methyl-N-phenylbenzamide	1.39794	1.02445	0.37350	0.237261	0.55395
041	2-methyl-N-phenylbenzamide	1.39794	1.13111	0.26683	0.207896	0.35583
042	N-cyclohexyl-N-isopropyl-4-methyloctanamide	1.39794	0.75572	0.64222	0.250761	1.00960
043	N,N-dicyclohexyl-4-methyloctanamide	1.39794	1.61953	-0.22159	0.224675	-0.31303
044	DEET	-1.28400	-0.18442	-1.09958	0.094401	-1.15937
046	dibutyl fumarate	-1.32790	-1.64387	0.31597	0.169501	0.37898
047	2-hydroxyethyl 2-hydroxy	0.39794	-0.07708	0.47502	0.158037	0.55528
048	2-chlorophenethyl alcohol	-0.99568	-1.08801	0.09233	0.087961	0.09666
049	2-bromophenethyl alcohol	-1.30980	-1.22933	-0.08047	0.088893	-0.08433
051	2-anilinoethanol	0.27300	-0.31728	0.59029	0.123570	0.64750
052	3-phenyl-1-propanol	-0.39147	-0.60156	0.21009	0.089761	0.22036
054	1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1-naphthol	-1.10791	-0.80823	-0.29968	0.111722	-0.32301
055	2-phenoxyethanol	-0.24949	-0.28409	0.03460	0.133027	0.03855
056	2-(N-ethylanilino)-ethanol	-0.80688	-0.83059	0.02372	0.097683	0.02511
057	2-(p-chlorophenoxy)-ethanol	-0.65956	-0.47157	-0.18798	0.091372	-0.19753
058	2-cyclohexyl-cyclohexanol	-0.35952	-0.90643	0.54691	0.145750	0.62357
059	2-phenyl-cyclohexanol	-1.32790	-1.32342	-0.00449	0.175690	-0.00546

060	1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-naphthol	-1.20761	-0.87980	-0.32781	0.143457	-0.37213
061	2-(2-bromophenyl)-1,3-dioxolane	-0.80688	-0.92361	0.11674	0.102458	0.12429
062	(2-iodophenyl)methanol	-1.15490	-1.37006	0.21516	0.119814	0.23465
063	2-nonanone	-0.35952	-0.60951	0.24999	0.127559	0.27597
064	2-undecanone	-0.96257	-1.11930	0.15673	0.135556	0.17538
065	valencene	-0.86012	-0.53342	-0.32670	0.215621	-0.44695
066	methyl salicylate	-0.50585	-0.53321	0.02737	0.109452	0.02940
069	thymol	-1.50864	-1.22363	-0.28501	0.125456	-0.31357
070	carvacrol methyl ether	-1.20066	-0.84088	-0.35978	0.095923	-0.38001
071	2-nonanol	-1.18046	-1.24781	0.06735	0.103839	0.07184
	Minimum	-1.50864	-1.64387	-1.09958	0.073039	-1.15937
	Maximum	1.39794	1.61953	0.80181	0.250761	1.00960
	Mean	-0.48422	-0.48422	0.00000	0.134268	0.01006
	Median	-0.73993	-0.59750	0.03460	0.126738	0.03855

Outlier compounds: **(006)** N,2-diethyl-N-(2-methyl-2-propenyl)butanimide, **(010)** N-ethyl-2,2-dimethyl-N-(2-methyl-2-propenyl)propanamide, **(031)** Hexahydro-1-(1-oxohexyl)-1H-azepine, **(035)** N-butyl-N-ethyl-cinnamamide, **(039)** 3-cyclohexyl-N-methyl-N-octylpropanamide, **(045)** 2-methyl-4-nitro-3-nonanol, **(050)** 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, **(053)** 1,2-pentanediol, **(067)** carvacrol, **(068)** benzyl benzoate.

Figure SM5_A3. Calculated versus observed minimum effective dosage (MED, $\mu\text{mol}/\text{cm}^2$) values for carboxamides repellency model.

Table SM5_A4. Comparison of predicted MED values, and bioassay results for selected compounds.

ID	Case	MED _{obs}	MED _{pred} ^a	MED _{pred} ^b
156	X4	0.078	0.010	0.03
157	X5	0.156	0.091	0.067
158	X10	1.25	0.064	0.33
159	X16	0.261	0.024	0.303
160	X17	1.667	0.322	0.082
161	X23	0.039	0.083	0.061
162	X25	1.87	0.050	0.198

a. Predicted MED values for our model. b. Predicted MED values for model of Oliferenko et al.

SM5_A5. Structure data set (carboxamides proposed by Oliferenko et al.)

	(022)	(023)	(024)
 (028)			
 (032)			
 (036)			
 (040)			
 (044)			
 (048)			
 (052)			
 (056)			

SM5_A6. Structure data set used for external validation (carboxamides proposed by Oliferenko et al.)

SM5_B) 34 carboxamides tested for their repellency properties against the three most common species of cockroach.

Gaudin J-M, Lander T, & Nikolaenko O (2008) Carboxamides Combining Favorable Olfactory Properties with Insect Repellency. *Chemistry & Biodiversity* 5(4):617-635.

Table SM5_B1. Prediction model and statistical parameters of derivatives carboxamides to the *Blattella germanica*.

Variable	Coefficients					
	Beta	Std.Err.	B	Std.Err.	t(20)	p-level
Intercept			103.8941	32.06436	3.24018	0.004102
3F1Q	-0.92235	0.113338	-30.3741	3.73233	-8.13810	0.000000
1N8V	1.51257	0.296293	54.4449	10.66504	5.10499	0.000054
3OGN	-1.14698	0.378305	-33.1950	10.94859	-3.03190	0.006585
3R10	1.34249	0.321953	48.7714	11.69627	4.16982	0.000473
3PM2	-1.24744	0.449834	-40.9643	14.77200	-2.77311	0.011734

Regression summary for dependent variable %PR: R = 0.89901030; R² = 0.80821952; Adjusted R² = 0.76027440; F(5,20) = 16.857; p < 0.00000; Std.Error of estimate = 11.728.

Table SM5_B2. PR observed and obtained values in the QSAR study for the training set.

ID	Case	Observed	Predicted	Residual	Std.Err.	Deleted
072	AC1-AM5	70.0000	65.3865	4.6135	4.820491	5.5513
074	AC1-AM8	20.0000	31.7713	-11.7713	7.046258	-18.4204
075	AC1-AM9	10.0000	26.2682	-16.2682	6.343297	-22.9951
076	AC2-AM3	97.0000	81.5176	15.4824	4.340896	17.9401
078	AC5-AM1	95.0000	75.8538	19.1462	3.925079	21.5612
079	AC5-AM3	100.0000	108.6094	-8.6094	4.823028	-10.3618
080	AC5-AM4	55.0000	64.5075	-9.5075	3.637094	-10.5191
081	AC5-AM5	40.0000	37.4370	2.5631	6.567879	3.7342
082	AC5-AM6	88.0000	89.5631	-1.5631	6.473719	-2.2481
083	AC6-AM1	100.0000	90.3219	9.6781	6.344048	13.6813
084	AC6-AM3	80.0000	80.6845	-0.6845	6.383745	-0.9727
085	AC6-AM4	80.0000	77.0052	2.9948	5.491466	3.8358
087	AC6-AM6	85.0000	96.8467	-11.8467	6.906317	-18.1356
089	AC6-AM9	95.0000	94.9731	0.0269	7.783439	0.0481
090	AC1-AM1	72.0000	93.4532	-21.4532	4.868763	-25.9204
091	AC6-AM8	75.0000	81.1796	-6.1796	3.930110	-6.9613
092	AC4-AM3	97.0000	100.2981	-3.2981	4.385708	-3.8343
094	AC10-AM1	97.0000	76.3047	20.6954	4.827688	24.9175
095	AC10-AM3	90.0000	84.5344	5.4656	7.005626	8.4977
098	AC2-AM1	80.0000	88.5234	-8.5233	4.398893	-9.9187
099	AC4-AM8	60.0000	47.0108	12.9892	5.372219	16.4384
100	AC1-AM10	98.0000	103.5870	-5.5870	4.457365	-6.5303
101	AC7-AM1	90.0000	82.5244	7.4756	3.902315	8.4063
103	AC7-AM6	90.0000	89.0924	0.9076	8.448254	1.8865
104	AC2-AM2	85.0000	84.1198	0.8802	5.044682	1.0800
105	AC1-AM15	95.0000	92.6265	2.3736	5.102425	2.9277
	Minimum	10.0000	26.2682	-21.4532	3.637094	-25.9204
	Maximum	100.0000	108.6094	20.6954	8.448254	24.9175
	Mean	78.6154	78.6154	0.0000	5.485800	-0.2428
	Median	86.5000	83.3221	0.4536	5.073553	0.5641

Outlier compounds: (073) AC1-AM7, (077) AC2-AM5, (086) AC6-AM5, (088) AC6-AM7, (096)

AC12-AM1, (097) AC4-AM9, (102) AC7-AM3

Figure SM5_B3. Calculated versus observed repellency (%PR) values for carboxamides repellency model.

Table SM5_B4. Prediction model and statistical parameters of derivatives carboxamides to the *Periplaneta americana*.

Variable	Coefficients					
	Beta	Std.Err.	B	Std.Err.	t(23)	p-level
Intercept			241.0497	35.94431	6.70620	0.000001
2GTE	1.49706	0.300955	45.9386	9.23506	4.97437	0.000050
3OGN	-2.10390	0.411572	-57.2604	11.20145	-5.11188	0.000035
2GVS	1.34628	0.240434	75.6101	13.50337	5.59935	0.000011
2WC5	-2.03375	0.447525	-53.5738	11.78889	-4.54443	0.000145
3PM2	2.29108	0.473199	72.2126	14.91474	4.84169	0.000069
3R10	-0.79888	0.325150	-27.9885	11.39149	-2.45696	0.021978

Regression Summary for Dependent Variable %PR: $R = 0.87766197$; $R^2 = 0.77029053$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.71036632$; $F(6,23) = 12.854$; $p < .00000$; Std.Error of estimate = 11.146.

Table SM5_B5. PR observed and obtained values in the QSAR study for the training set.

ID	Case	Observed	Predicted	Residual	Std.Err.	Deleted
072	AC1-AM5	80.0000	66.6492	13.3508	4.423166	15.8463
073	AC1-AM7	70.0000	80.9922	-10.9922	3.286256	-12.0387
074	AC1-AM8	97.0000	96.2381	0.7619	5.057958	0.9595
075	AC1-AM9	50.0000	49.1975	0.8025	5.265466	1.0331
076	AC2-AM3	60.0000	71.5582	-11.5582	6.804217	-18.4245
077	AC2-AM5	85.0000	87.7590	-2.7589	5.037484	-3.4672
078	AC5-AM1	100.0000	102.5395	-2.5395	4.440186	-3.0185
079	AC5-AM3	95.0000	92.3348	2.6652	2.597934	2.8183
080	AC5-AM4	60.0000	84.8996	-24.8996	4.659307	-30.1721
081	AC5-AM5	70.0000	66.3528	3.6472	3.766656	4.1175
082	AC5-AM6	98.0000	78.3710	19.6290	7.172182	33.5005
084	AC6-AM3	80.0000	80.8370	-0.8370	4.943563	-1.0420
086	AC6-AM5	50.0000	45.7105	4.2895	6.562524	6.5655
088	AC6-AM7	98.0000	80.4860	17.5140	5.143876	22.2538
089	AC6-AM9	10.0000	30.0458	-20.0458	7.377791	-35.6783
090	AC1-AM1	99.0000	106.5047	-7.5047	5.287008	-9.6835
091	AC6-AM8	95.0000	104.0796	-9.0796	5.991710	-12.7699
092	AC4-AM3	97.0000	100.4383	-3.4383	4.957783	-4.2864
094	AC10-AM1	95.0000	89.7057	5.2943	6.467401	7.9817
095	AC10-AM3	95.0000	100.6466	-5.6466	6.323673	-8.3269
096	AC12-AM1	98.0000	89.6812	8.3188	3.682974	9.3384
097	AC4-AM9	90.0000	85.3004	4.6996	4.932653	5.8442
098	AC2-AM1	98.0000	91.5386	6.4614	4.526083	7.7372
099	AC4-AM8	80.0000	72.7165	7.2836	5.179333	9.2894
100	AC1-AM10	98.0000	99.4889	-1.4889	6.232646	-2.1662
101	AC7-AM1	70.0000	76.7154	-6.7154	4.612291	-8.1029
102	AC7-AM3	98.0000	102.0743	-4.0743	5.844107	-5.6191
103	AC7-AM6	98.0000	99.7728	-1.7728	7.352544	-3.1385
104	AC2-AM2	85.0000	78.7443	6.2557	5.351546	8.1299
105	AC1-AM15	97.0000	84.6218	12.3782	4.432330	14.7033
	Minimum	10.0000	30.0458	-24.8996	2.597934	-35.6783
	Maximum	100.0000	106.5047	19.6290	7.377791	33.5005
	Mean	83.2000	83.2000	0.0000	5.257088	-0.2605
	Median	95.0000	85.1000	-0.0375	5.100917	-0.0412

Outlier compounds: (083) AC6-AM1, (085) AC6-AM4, (087) AC6-AM6.

Figure SM5_B6. Calculated versus observed repellency (%PR) values for carboxamides repellency model.

SM5_B7. Structure data set (carboxamides proposed by Gaudin et al.)

SM5_C) 35 constituent compound plant-derived, which were evaluated for repellency on forearms of human volunteers against *Anopheles gambiae* sensu strict.

Omolo MO, Okinyo D, Ndiege IO, Lwande W, & Hassanali A (2004) Repellency of essential oils of some Kenyan plants against *Anopheles gambiae*. *Phytochemistry* 65(20):2797-2802

Table SM5_C1. Prediction model and statistical parameters of compound plant-derived to the *Anopheles gambiae*.

Variable	Coefficients					
	Beta	Std.Err.	B	Std.Err.	t(25)	p-level
Intercept			-0.007056	0.001878	-3.75680	0.000923
2GTE	-1.33987	0.302520	-0.002499	0.000564	-4.42904	0.000164
1QWV	0.81370	0.177107	0.001737	0.000378	4.59438	0.000107
3F1Q	0.52402	0.197062	0.000681	0.000256	2.65914	0.013471
3R10	-0.44170	0.184469	-0.001102	0.000460	-2.39442	0.024466

Regression summary for dependent variable RD₅₀: R = 0.86603381; R² = 0.75001455; Adjusted R² =

0.71001688; F(4,25)=18.751; p<.00000; Std.Error of estimate = 0.00053.

Table SM5_C2. RD₅₀ observed and obtained values in the QSAR study for the training set.

ID	Case	Observed	Predicted	Residual	Std.Err.	Deleted
106	Camphene	0.002210	0.001553	0.000657	0.000184	0.000745
107	Limonene	0.001800	0.001484	0.000316	0.000120	0.000333
108	b-Pinene	0.001560	0.001869	-0.000309	0.000161	-0.000340
110	aTerpinene	0.002400	0.002113	0.000287	0.000144	0.000309
111	c-Terpinene	0.002740	0.002481	0.000259	0.000250	0.000331
112	a-Terpinolene	0.002550	0.002239	0.000311	0.000245	0.000393
116	Perillyl alcohol	0.000063	0.000783	-0.000720	0.000210	-0.000851
118	cis-Carveol	0.000100	0.001084	-0.000984	0.000235	-0.001221
119	Geraniol	0.000110	-0.000080	0.000190	0.000233	0.000235
120	a-Terpineol	0.001280	0.000989	0.000291	0.000231	0.000358
121	Eugenol	0.001320	0.000946	0.000374	0.000202	0.000436
122	Terpen-4-ol	0.001480	0.002062	-0.000582	0.000149	-0.000631
123	Linalool	0.001530	0.000689	0.000841	0.000172	0.000938
124	Citronellal	0.000220	0.000989	-0.000769	0.000214	-0.000916
125	Perillaldehyde	0.000320	0.001274	-0.000954	0.000151	-0.001037
126	Camphor	0.001400	0.001786	-0.000386	0.000211	-0.000457
127	Verbenone	0.001560	0.001414	0.000146	0.000155	0.000160
128	Fenchone	0.001890	0.001573	0.000317	0.000162	0.000350
129	Carvone	0.001260	0.001172	0.000088	0.000190	0.000101
131	Limonene oxide	0.001470	0.001416	0.000054	0.000129	0.000057
132	1,8-Cineole	0.001240	0.002276	-0.001036	0.000223	-0.001254
133	Citral	0.001310	0.001135	0.000175	0.000148	0.000190
134	a-Fenchyl alcohol	0.001350	0.001193	0.000157	0.000147	0.000170
135	Borneol	0.001650	0.001210	0.000440	0.000192	0.000506
136	Myrtenol	0.001540	0.001393	0.000147	0.000181	0.000166
137	Geranyl acetate	0.003260	0.002808	0.000452	0.000409	0.001092
138	Thujone	0.001450	0.001117	0.000333	0.000148	0.000361
139	Myrtenal	0.001650	0.001714	-0.000064	0.000180	-0.000072
140	Aromadendrene	0.004980	0.004881	0.000099	0.000506	0.000965
141	4-Isopropylbenzaldehy	0.001630	0.001761	-0.000131	0.000233	-0.000162
	Minimum	0.000063	-0.000080	-0.001036	0.000120	-0.001254
	Maximum	0.004980	0.004881	0.000841	0.000506	0.001092
	Mean	0.001577	0.001577	0.000000	0.000204	0.000042
	Median	0.001505	0.001415	0.000152	0.000187	0.000180

Outlier compounds: (109) p-Cymene, (113) a-Pinene, (117) cis-Verbenol, (130) Caryophyllene oxide.

Figure SM5_C3. Calculated versus observed RD_{50} values for compound plant-derived repellency model.

SM5_C4. Structure data set (constituent compound plant-derived proposed by Omolo et al.)

	(117)	(118)	
 (123)			
 (127)			
 (131)			
 (135)			
 (139)			
 (141)			

SM5_D) DEET and 13 plant-derived sesquiterpenes isolated, purified, and assayed for spatial repellency against the yellow fever mosquito *A. aegypti*.

Paluch G, Grodnitzky J, Bartholomay L, & Coats J (2009) Quantitative structure-activity relationship of botanical sesquiterpenes: spatial and contact repellency to the yellow fever mosquito, *Aedes aegypti*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 57, 7618-7625.

Table SM5_D1. Prediction model and statistical parameters of compound plant-derived sesquiterpenes to the *A. aegypti*.

Variable	Coefficients					
	Beta	Std.Err.	B	Std.Err.	t(7)	p-level
Intercept			2.427176	0.132961	18.25486	0.000000
3R10	1.17738	0.135019	0.171482	0.019665	8.72015	0.000052
3PM2	-1.20248	0.148671	-0.135923	0.016805	-8.08814	0.000085
3S0D	0.34657	0.120419	0.028771	0.009997	2.87803	0.023718

Regression summary for dependent variable Log(%PR_{60min}): R = 0.96285788; R² = 0.92709530; Adjusted R² = 0.89585043; F(3,7 = 29.672 *p*<.00024; Std.Error of estimate = 0.02160.

Table SM5_D2. %PR_{60min} observed and obtained values in the QSAR study for the training set.

ID	Case	Observed	Predicted	Residual	Std.Err.	Deleted
143	alpha-santalol	1.817565	1.837466	-0.019901	0.008578	-0.023628
144	alpha-bisabolol	1.786041	1.786815	-0.000773	0.010832	-0.001033
146	elemol	1.925312	1.881535	0.043777	0.007973	0.050684
147	beta-eudesmol	1.859138	1.854892	0.004247	0.012072	0.006176
148	hedycaryol	2.000000	2.008499	-0.008499	0.016965	-0.022191
149	valerianol	1.860338	1.847053	0.013285	0.011063	0.018011
150	fokienol	1.911690	1.902922	0.008768	0.019921	0.058766
151	trans-nerolidol	1.794488	1.808197	-0.013709	0.010638	-0.018100
153	10-epi- γ -eudesmol	1.914872	1.934314	-0.019442	0.011903	-0.027924
154	DEET	1.856729	1.858107	-0.001378	0.014691	-0.002564
155	turmeronee	1.796574	1.802949	-0.006375	0.013706	-0.010673
	Minimum	1.786041	1.786815	-0.019901	0.007973	-0.027924
	Maximum	2.000000	2.008499	0.043777	0.019921	0.058766
	Mean	1.865704	1.865704	0.000000	0.012577	0.002502
	Median	1.859138	1.854892	-0.001378	0.011903	-0.002564

Outlier compounds: (142) Nootkatone, **(145)** farnesol, **(152)** elemene.

Figure SM5_D3. Calculated versus observed %PR_{60min} values for compound plant-derived sesquiterpenes repellency model.

Table SM5_D4. Prediction model and statistical parameters of compound plant-derived sesquiterpenes to the *A. aegypti*.

Variable	Coefficients					
	Beta	Std.Err.	B	Std.Err.	t(7)	p-level
Intercept			1.306189	0.198555	6.57847	0.000310
3F1Q	-0.983134	0.115278	-0.106614	0.012501	-8.52839	0.000060
3N7H	0.345893	0.126105	0.063031	0.022980	2.74290	0.028798
3S0D	-0.184499	0.128002	-0.034719	0.024088	-1.44138	0.192676

Regression summary for dependent variable Log(%PR_{120min}): R = 0.95677909; R² = 0.91542622;

Adjusted R² = 0.87918032; F(3,7) = 25.256; p < 0.00040; Std.Error of estimate = 0.03097.

Table SM5_D5. %PR_{120min} observed and obtained values in the QSAR study for the training set.

ID	Case	Observed	Predicted	Residual	Std.Err.	Deleted
142	nootkatone	1.713490	1.715505	-0.002014	0.024020	-0.005054
143	alpha-santalol	1.905796	1.880439	0.025357	0.018312	0.038988
144	alpha-bisabolol	1.922206	1.900093	0.022113	0.016932	0.031541
145	farnesol	1.705008	1.739607	-0.034599	0.020586	-0.061987
146	elemol	1.925312	1.957168	-0.031856	0.013985	-0.040016
147	β-eudesmol	1.911690	1.918153	-0.006463	0.017446	-0.009467
148	hedycaryol	1.989895	1.997977	-0.008082	0.019989	-0.013852
149	valerianol	1.913284	1.913154	0.000130	0.013543	0.000161
153	10-epi-γ-eudesmol	1.914872	1.873191	0.041681	0.009958	0.046487
154	DEET	1.904174	1.879902	0.024272	0.024078	0.061362
155	turmeronee	1.905256	1.935795	-0.030539	0.021261	-0.057760
	Minimum	1.705008	1.715505	-0.034599	0.009958	-0.061987
	Maximum	1.989895	1.997977	0.041681	0.024078	0.061362
	Mean	1.882817	1.882817	0.000000	0.018192	-0.000873
	Median	1.911690	1.900093	-0.002014	0.018312	-0.005054

Outlier compounds: (150) Fokienol, (151) trans-nerolidol, (152) elemene.

Figure SM5_D6. Calculated versus observed %PR_{120min} values for compound plant-derived sesquiterpenes repellency model.

SM5_D7. Structure Data set (plant-derived sesquiterpenes proposed by Paluch et al.)

3. Case study 4 (SM6)

SM6_A. Structure of the compounds used in study Simulation Virtual Screening.

001. <i>n</i> -Hexanol 		
004. Camphene 		
007. Myrcene 		
010. Δ -3-Carene 		
013. β -Phellandrene 		
016. γ -Terpinene 		
019. <i>n</i> -Undecane 		
022. <i>trans</i> - β -Terpineol 		
025. Dihydro carveol 		
028. <i>n</i> -Octyl 2-methylbutyrate 		
031. δ -Elemene 		

034. β -Elemene	035. β -Longipinene	036. (<i>E</i>)-Caryophyllene
037. Lavandulyl isobutyrate	038. <i>cis</i> -Thujopsene	039. Aromadendrene
040. α -Humulene	041. α -Acoradiene	042. γ -Himachalene
043. Germacrene D	044. Citronellyl isobutyrate	045. <i>trans</i> - β -Guaiene
046. (<i>Z</i>)- α -Bisabolene	047. γ -Cadinene	048. (<i>Z</i>)- γ -Bisabolene
049. β -Sesquiphellandrene	050. Germacrene B	051. Spathulenol
052. Globulol	053. (<i>Z</i>)-Sesquilandulol	054. γ -Eudesmol

055. β -Acorenol	056. Himachalol	057. (Z,Z)-Farnesol
058. Phytol	059. <i>iso</i> -Bergaptene	060. Octadecanol
061. Pentanal	062. (<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenal	063. 1-Octen-3-one
064. 1-Octen-3-ol	065. Limonene	066. 1,8-Cineole
067. <i>n</i> -Nonanal	068. (<i>E</i>)-Tagetone	069. Menthofuran
070. (2 <i>E</i> , 4 <i>E</i>)-2,4-Decadienal	071. <i>n</i> -Undecanol	072. β -Cubebene
073. (<i>E</i>)- β -damascenone	074. Sativene	075. (<i>E</i>)- β -Damascone
076. <i>trans</i> - α -Bergamotene	077. (<i>Z</i>)- β -Farnesene	078. (<i>E</i>)- β -Farnesene
079. (<i>E</i>)-2-Dodecenal	080. Ferutidine	081. β -Selinene

082. α -Muurolene	083. δ -Cadinene	084. (<i>E</i>)- γ -Bisabolene
085. Dodecanoic acid	086. Caryophyllene oxide	087. <i>epi</i> - α -Muurolool
088. Cubenol	089. β -Eudesmol	090. α -Eudesmol
091. α -Cadinol	092. Selin-11-en-4 α -ol	093. <i>n</i> -Octyl butyrate
094. (<i>2E</i> , <i>4E</i>)-Farnesol	095. 14-Hydroxy- α -muurolene	096. 6,10,14-Trimethyl-2-pentadecanone
097. Hexadecanoic acid	098. Isovaleric acid	099. α -Thujene
100. Borneol	101. Citronellol	102. Bornyl acetate

103. Myrtenyl acetate	104. α -Terpinyl acetate	105. Citronellyl acetate
106. α -Gurjunene	107. β -Gurjunene	108. <i>allo</i> -Aromadendrene
109. <i>Dehydro</i> -Aromadendrene	110. 9- <i>epi</i> -(<i>E</i>)-Caryophyllene	111. β -Chamigrene
112. <i>cis</i> - β -Guaiene	113. Viridiflorene	114. β -Bisabolene
115. Kessane	116. Elemol	117. Guaiol
118. 10- <i>epi</i> - γ -Eudesmol	119. Acetoxyvaleranone	120. <i>epi</i> - α -Cadinol
121. Hinesol	122. Valerenal	123. Valeranone

124. <i>epi-α</i> -Bisabolol 		
127. (2 <i>Z</i>)-pentenol 		
130. Octyl adipate 		
133. Neophytadiene 		
136. 6-heptyltetrahydro-2H-pyran-2-one 		
139. (3 <i>E</i> ,5 <i>E</i>)-pseudoionone 		
142. Cyclohexadecanolide 		
145. Nonadecane 		

148. 3-Heptadecanone 		
151. (2Z)-pentadecenol 		
154. Ethyl acetate 		
157. (E,Z)-farnesol 		
160. 2-heptenone 		
163. Pentyl acetate 		
166. Benzaldehyde 		
169. 2-propyl thiophene 		
172. 2-pentylfuran 		
175. 2-(methoxymethyl)-3,5-dimethyl-2,5-cyclohexadien-1,4-dione 		

178. γ -hexalactone 	179. (2E)-octenal	180. Vinyl caproate
181. <i>trans</i> -linalool oxide 	182. (3E,5Z)-octadien-2-one 	183. Hexanoic acid
184. 5-formyl-2-pentylthiophene 	185. (3E,5E)-octadien-2-one 	186. Linalool
187. Geraniol 	188. (2E,4E)-octadienal 	189. Phenylethylalcohol
190. <i>trans-p</i> -mentha-2,8-dien-1-ol 	191. Pentadecanal 	192. Heptanoic acid
193. Limona ketone 	194. <i>cis-p</i> -mentha-2,8-dien-1-ol 	195. (3E)-nonen-2-one
196. Camphor 	197. (E)-5-ethyl-6-methyl-3-hepten-2-one 	198. Lilac aldehyde
199. Isobutyl valerate 	200. (2E)-nonenal 	201. <i>cis</i> -linalyl oxide
202. Neryl acetate 	203. Terpinen-4-ol 	204. Menthol

205. Octanoic acid 		
208. Dodecane 		
211. Decanoic acid 		
214. Methyl pelargonate 		
217. <i>cis</i> -carveol 		
220. <i>p</i> -anis aldehyde 		
223. Pelargonic acid 		
226. 2-undecanone-(2 <i>E</i> ,4 <i>Z</i>)-decadienal	227. Ethyl hexanoate 	

229. 4-vinyl-o-guaiacol 		
232. γ -nonalactone 		
235. Methyl eugenol 		
238. 2-dodecanone 		
241. <i>Ar</i> -curcumene 		
244. α -selinene 		
247. Humulene epoxide II 		
250. Hexahydrofarnesol 		

253. (3Z)-butylidene phthalide	254. Cadalene	255. (Z)-ligustilide
256. Myristic acid	257. n-octanol	258. cis-Linalool oxide
259. Methyl linoleate	260. Methyl oleate	261. Methyl phytol
262. Methyl stearate	263. Ethyl phytol	264. Linoleic acid
265. Heptacosane	266. Valerenol	267. β -Linalool
268. Myristicin	269. α -Bourbonene	270. α -Oplopanone
271. α -Chamigrene	272. Hexadecane	273. 3-Eicosyne

<p>274. <i>n</i>-Butyl butyrate</p>		
<p>277. <i>n</i>-Butyl isobutyrate</p>		
<p>280. 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p>		
<p>283. 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>		
<p>286. <i>p</i>-methyl-benzaldehyde</p>		
<p>289. Propanoic acid, butyl ester</p>		
<p>292. 2,3-dihydro-benzofuran</p>		
<p>295. 2,7-dimethyl-1-octanol</p>		
<p>298. 2-Undecanone</p>		

301. 2,2-dimethyl-1-(2-hydroxy-1-methylethyl)propanoate 		
304. Isopropyl isovalerate 		
307. Dodecanal 		
310. (<i>E</i>)-Nerolidol 		
313. (<i>Z</i>)-3-hexenal 		
316. <i>trans-p</i> -menth-2-en-1-ol 		
319. <i>cis-p</i> -menth-2-en-1-ol 		
322. <i>trans</i> -carvone oxide 		
325. β -himachalene 		

328. Propyl butyrate 		
331. 2,2,4-Trimethyl-pentadiol 		
334. 1,1,6-Trimethyl-1,2-dihydronaphthalene 		
337. 4,6-Dimethyl-dodecane 		
340. 1-[2,3,6-Trimethyl-phenyl]-2-butanone 		
343. Docosane 		
346. (E)-beta-ocimene 		
349. trans-verbenol 		
352. Carvenone 		

355. <i>p</i> -mentha-1(7),5-dien-2-ol 		
358. β -Bisabolol 		
361. τ -Muurolol 		
364. α -Ionone 		
367. Ledene oxide 		
370. Croweacin 		
373. (<i>Z</i>)-3-hexenol 		
376. Yomogi alcohol 		

379. Hotrienol 		
382. Veratrole 		
385. δ -terpineol 		
388. Myrtenal 		
391. <i>cis</i> -chrysanthenyl acetate 		
394. <i>trans</i> -carvyl acetate 		
397. <i>trans</i> -myrtenol acetate 		
400. γ -curcumene 		
403. <i>cis</i> -dracunculifoliol	404. Palustrol	405. Viridiflorol

406. Isolongifolan-7- α -ol	407. 1-epi-cubanol	408. Zingiberenol
409. 3-thujopsanone	410. α -bisabolol	411. Methyl carvacrol
412. Chamazulene	413. Xanthorrhizol	414. Thymoquinone
415. <i>cis</i> -Salvene	416. <i>trans</i> -Salvene	417. Tricyclene
418. <i>o</i> -Cymene	419. <i>cis</i> -Ocimene	420. α -Terpinolene
421. β -Thujone	422. α -Thujone	423. Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptan-3-one
424. Methyl thymol	425. Guaiene	426. Naphthalene
427. α -Guaiene	428. <i>trans</i> - β -bergamotene	429. Thymohydroquinone

430. 5-methylenenorbornene	431. Santolina triene	432. Verbenene
433. ethyl propanoate	434. 1-octene	435. α -fenchene
436. <i>m</i> -cymenene	437. <i>cis</i> - β -terpineol	438. <i>neo</i> -3-thujanol
439. Citronellal	440. (<i>Z</i>)-ocimene	441. (<i>E</i>)-ocimene
442. Methyl citronellate	443. <i>neo</i> -3-thujyl acetate	444. Patchoulene
445. Cyperene	446. α -cedrene	447. β -cedrene
448. Selina-3,7-diene	449. <i>cis</i> -sesquibabinene hydrate	450. 6,11-oxidoacor-4-ene
451. α -agarofuran	452. Geranyl- <i>n</i> -butyrate	453. Ledol

454. β -caryophyllene alcohol 		
457. Pentadec-1-ene 		
460. Heptadeca-1,8-diene 		
463. 1- <i>p</i> -Menthene 		
466. α -Pinene oxide 		
469. Caran-3 β -ol 		
472. Muurolo-4,10(14)-dien-1 β -ol 		
475. <i>ar</i> -turmerol 		

478. Cryptone	479. Verbenone	480. Thymyl methyl ether
481. Pulegone	482. Cuminal	483. Myrtanol
484. Piperitone	485. Phenylethyl acetate	486. Nonanoic acid
487. Isobornyl acetate	488. Piperitenone	489. α -Longipinene
490. Thymyl acetate	491. Teferdine	492. Geranyl acetate
493. Linalyl butyrate	494. β -Copaene	495. γ -Elemene
496. Cinnamyl acetate	497. β -Humulene	498. γ -Humulene
499. Valencene	500. Bicyclogermacrene	501. β -Cadinene

502. <i>cis</i> -Calamenene	503. Zonarene	504. Caryophylla-4(12),8(13)-dien-5 β -ol
505. (<i>Z</i>)-Isoeugenol acetate	506. β -Calacorene	507. Germacrene-D-4-ol
508. 2-Phenylethyl tiglate	509. <i>cis</i> -Isolongifolanone	510. α -Acorenol
511. Torreyol	512. Bulnesol	513. Juniper camphor
514. β -Sinensal	515. (<i>E,E</i>)-Farnesyl acetate	516. Caryophylla-4(14),8(15)-dien-5-ol
517. 1-Eicosene	518. Manoyl oxide	519. Palmitoleic acid
520. Palmitic acid	521. Kaurene	522. Eicosane

523. Tetracosane 		
526. Cubebol 		
529. β -Atlantone 		
532. γ -Gurjunene 		
535. <i>trans</i> -Calamenene 		
538. Triacontane 		
541. <i>p</i> -Menth-1-en-8-ol 		
544. Cuminol 		

547. <i>trans</i> - α -bisabolene 		
550. Nothoapiole 		
553. Neral 		
556. Acorenone B 		
559. Nicotine 		
562. (<i>Z</i>)- β -Santalene 		
565. (<i>E</i>)-3-Hexen-1-ol 		
568. (<i>Z</i>)-4-Hexen-1-ol	569. (<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl formate	570. Hexyl acetate

571. (Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate 	572. (E)-2-Hexenyl acetate 	573. Hexyl propionate
574. (Z)-3-Hexenyl propionate 	575. (E)-2-Hexenyl propionate 	576. Hexyl butyrate
577. (Z)-3-Hexenyl butyrate 	578. (E)-2-Hexenyl butyrate 	579. Hexyl isobutyrate
580. (E)-2-Hexenyl isobutyrate 	581. (Z)-3-Hexenyl 2-methylbutyrate 	582. (E)-2-Hexenyl 2-methylbutyrate
583. (Z)-3-Hexenyl 3-methylbutyrate 	584. (E)-2-Hexenyl 3-methylbutyrate 	585. Hexyl tiglate
586. (Z)-3-Hexenyl tiglate 	587. (E)-2-Hexenyl tiglate 	588. Hexyl hexanoate
589. (Z)-3-Hexenyl hexanoate 	590. (E)-2-Hexenyl hexanoate 	591. (Z)-3-Hexenyl benzoate
592. (E)-4-octene 	593. trans-pinocamphone 	594. 3,9-epoxy-p-menth-1-ene
595. Hydroxy citronellal 	596. (Z)-β-damascenone 	597. (Z)-ethyl cinnamate

598. 7- <i>epi</i> -sesquithujene	599. (<i>E</i>)-amyl cinnamic alcohol 	600. Farnesol (<i>Z,E</i>)
601. Isopulegone 	602. <i>cis</i> -Piperitone epoxide 	603. Piperitenone epoxide
604. Isopentyl acetate 	605. <i>S</i> -ethyl pentanethioate 	606. Thuja-2,4(10)-diene
607. Curzerene 	608. (<i>E</i>)-3-hexenol acetate 	609. 3-methylbutyl butanoate
610. 3-methylbutyl-2-methylpropanoate 	611. 1,4-cineole 	612. butyl-2-methylbutanoate
613. <i>p</i> -cymenene 	614. isoamyl-2-methylbutyrate 	615. Chrysanthenone
616. <i>trans</i> -sabinol 	617. <i>cis</i> -verbenol 	618. Sabinaketone
619. Isopinocampone 	620. α -thujenal 	621. dihydro- <i>ar</i> -turmerone
622. <i>trans</i> -muurola-4(14),5-diene	623. <i>trans</i> -sesquisabinene hydrate	624. Linalyl acetate

625. 4-methoxycinnamaldehyde 		
628. <i>trans</i> -1,4-Dimethylcyclohexane 		
631. Ethylcyclohexane 		
634. (<i>Z</i>)-4-Heptenal 		
637. <i>trans</i> -2-(2-Pentenyl)furan 		
640. <i>trans</i> -muurola-3,5-diene 		
643. 2,2,4-Trimethyl-3-cyclohexene-1-carbaldehyde 		
646. <i>p</i> -Ethylguaiacol 		

<p>649. <i>cis</i>-Jasmone</p>		
<p>652. Tetradecanoic acid</p>		
<p>655. Dehydroelsholtzia ketone</p>		
<p>658. Nonanol</p>		
<p>661. Borneol propionate</p>		
<p>664. Benzofurane</p>		
<p>667. (<i>2E,6Z</i>)-Nonadienal</p>		
<p>670. Methyl linolenate</p>		

673. 2-Hexanone 		
676. 2-Hexanol 		
679. 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline 		
682. 2,3-octanedione 		
685. 1,4-dichlorobenzene 		
688. <i>o</i> -cresol 		
691. 3,5-octadien-2-one 		
694. 1-(3-methylphenyl)-ethanone 		
697. Benzoic acid 		
700. 2-decanone 		

703. 2-methylnaphthalene 		
706. 1-methylnaphthalene 		
709. (2 <i>E</i>)-undecenal 		
712. Biphenyl 		
715. Lauric acid 		
718. Isoterpinolene 		
721. Santalol 		
724. Khusinol 		
727. Isopulegol 		

730. <i>trans</i> -sabinyl acetate 		
733. 2-Isopropenyl-5-methyl-4-hexenylacetate 		
736. <i>Epi</i> -bicyclosesquiphellandrene 		
739. Cuparene 		
742. (<i>Z</i>)-caryophyllene 		
745. 7- <i>epi</i> - α -selinene 		
748. <i>cis</i> -Limonene oxide 		

<p>751. Dihydrolinalyl acetate</p>		
<p>754. Campherenol</p>		
<p>757. <i>p</i>-Mentha-2,4(8)-diene</p>		
<p>760. Isolatedene</p>		
<p>763. β-Acoradiene</p>		
<p>766. α-Copaen-11-ol</p>		
<p>769. Eudesma-4(15),7-dien-1β-ol</p>		
<p>772. Junenol</p>		

<p>775. (<i>E,E</i>)- Hexa-2,4-dienal</p>		
<p>778. Perilla alcohol</p>		
<p>781. Methyl-(<i>Z</i>)-isoeugenol</p>		
<p>784. (<i>E</i>)-Nerolidol acetate</p>		
<p>787. Salvia-4(14)-en-1-one</p>		
<p>790. Seychellene</p>		

SM6_B. Name and references reported for the components of essential oils used in the Simulation Virtual Screening.

No	Nombre	Referencia ^a
1	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	1/8/14/21/30/34/37
2	<i>n</i> -Nonane	1
3	α -Pinene	1/4/3/8/9/10/11/12/13/14/15/16/18/19/22/23/24/25/27/28/31/32/33/34/35/37/38/40/41/43/7
4	Camphene	1/3/8/10/11/14/15/16/18/19/23/24/25/27/28/33/34/37/40
5	Sabinene	1/2/8/10/11/12/14/15/16/18/19/23/24/33/34/40/43
6	β -Pinene	1/2/3/4/8/10/11/13/14/15/16/18/19/23/24/25/26/27/28/31/33/34/35/37/38/39/40/41/43/7
7	Myrcene	1/2/4/9/10/11/15/16/18/19/23/24/14/28/31/33/34/37/40/27/30/32/41/43
8	<i>n</i> -Octanal	1/8/14/19/27/30/33/34/42/7
9	α -Phellandrene	1/9/11/14/15/18/19/24/27/28/31/33/34/37/38/40/10/41
10	Δ -3-Carene	1/11/14/14/15/24/28/33/34/39/40/32/41
11	α -Terpinene	1/4/8/9/10/11/14/15/16/22/23/24/27/28/31/33/38/40/41/43
12	<i>p</i> -Cymene	1/2/3/4/8/9/11/14/15/16/18/19/22/23/24/27/28/30/32/34/37/40/41/42/43/7
13	β -Phellandrene	1/8/10/11/18/19/24/27/28/31/34/40
14	(<i>Z</i>)- β -Ocimene	1/8/10/11/26/30/33/34/38/39/41
15	Dihydrotagetone	1
16	γ -Terpinene	1/4/8/9/10/11/14/15/16/18/23/24/26/27/28/31/32/33/34/37/40/41/42/43
17	<i>cis</i> -Sabinene hydrate	1/8/9/10/11/15/16/24/28/33/40
18	Piperitenone oxide	36
19	<i>n</i> -Undecane	1/17/27/29/30
20	Isopentyl-isovalerate	1/24/39/42
21	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl isobutyrate	1/21
22	<i>trans</i> - β -Terpineol	1
23	<i>meta</i> -Cymen-8-ol	1
24	α -Terpineol	1/2/4/5/8/10/11/15/16/19/23/25/27/28/30/31/33/34/36/37/39/40
25	Dihydro carveol	1/24
26	<i>n</i> -Decanal	1/4/6/16/27/30/33
27	Hexyl 2-methyl butyrate	1/42
28	<i>n</i> -Octyl 2-methylbutyrate	42
29	Carvotanacetone	1/22
30	Dec-9-en-1-ol	1
31	δ -Elemene	1/3/13/14/15/16/31/33/39
32	α -Copaene	1/2/8/12/13/1/184/15/16/19/24/26/31/34/35/37/38/39/40/27/14/15/16
33	β -Bourbonene	1/2/8/10/11/12/14/16/23/24/27/28/31/34/37/38/40
34	β -Elemene	1/2/3/4/8/12/13/14/15/18/19/26/27/31/33/34/35/37/39
35	β -Longipinene	1
36	(<i>E</i>)-Caryophyllene	1
37	Lavandulyl isobutyrate	1
38	<i>cis</i> -Thujopsene	1/34/27
39	Aromadendrene	1/2/10/13/16/22/27/37/40
40	α -Humulene	1/3/4/8/9/10/15/16/18/20/22/24/25/26/28/33/34/37/38/39/40
41	α -Acoradiene	1/8/34/39
42	γ -Himachalene	1/13/31/39
43	Germacrene D	1/2/3/5/8/10/11/14/15/18/23/24/27/28/29/31/34/35/37/38/39/7
44	Citronellyl isobutyrate	1
45	<i>trans</i> - β -Guaiene	1/31/39
46	(<i>Z</i>)- α -Bisabolene	1/22/33/38
47	γ -Cadinene	1/3/10/16/22/25/26/28/34/35/37/39/40/24/40
48	(<i>Z</i>)- γ -Bisabolene	1/18/33/34

49	β -Sesquiphellandrene	1/12/19/24/34/40
50	Germacrene B	1/3/9/14/15/18/19/40
51	Spathulenol	1/2/3/5/8/12/14/16/18/24/26/31/34/37/43/7
52	Globulol	1/3/8/12/14/16/22/24/26/31/35/37
53	(Z)-Sesquilavandulol	1
54	γ -Eudesmol	1/14/27/31
55	β -Acorenol	1
56	Himachalol	1/34
57	(Z,Z)-Farnesol	1/6/8
58	Phytol	1/6/8/5/17/34
59	iso-Bergaptene	1
60	Octadecanol	1
61	Pentanal	2/12
62	(E)-2-Hexenal	2/4/14/21/14/27/29/30/37
63	1-Octen-3-one	2
64	1-Octen-3-ol	2/4/5/10/14/23/28/30/35
65	Limonene	2/3/4/9/11/13/14/15/16/18/19/22/23/24/25/26/27/28/29/30/32/33/35/37/40/41/43/7
66	1,8-Cineole	2/8/10/11/14/16/18/19/23/24/25/28/36/37/38/41/43/7/27
67	n-Nonanal	2/4/6/8/24/27/29/30/33/34
68	(E)-Tagetone	2
69	Menthofuran	2
70	(E, E)-2,4-Decadienal	2/4/6/27/29/30
71	n-Undecanol	2
72	β -Cubebene	2/10/14/15/16/24/31/34/37/40
73	(E)- β -damascenone	2/4/6/8/17/27/29
74	Sativene	2/40
75	(E)- β -Damascone	2
76	trans- α -Bergamotene	2/14/16/19/33/34/38/27
77	(Z)- β -Farnesene	2/14/19/31/33/41
78	(E)- β -Farnesene	2/8/14/15/16/18/19/24/13/31/33/34/27/38
79	(E)-2-Dodecenal	2
80	Ferutidine	34
81	β -Selinene	2/3/4/10/13/14/15/18/27/37/39/40/7
82	α -Muurolene	2/8/13/14/15/16/22/24/28/27/30/31/37/40/15/27
83	δ -Cadinene	2/3/4/8/11/14/15/16/19/24/27/28/30/31/34/37/38/40/31/7
84	(E)- γ -Bisabolene	2/12/19/24/14/33/34/37
85	Dodecanoic acid	2/27
86	Caryophyllene oxide	2/4/5/8/9/10/13/14/15/16/18/24/26/27/31/32/34/35/36/37/39/40/28/38/43
87	epi- α -Muurolol	2/4/30/31
88	Cubenol	2/14/16/31/35
89	β -Eudesmol	2/3/4/14/16/19/27/40
90	α -Eudesmol	2/19/27
91	α -Cadinol	2/4/14/16/26/27/28/30/34/37
92	Selin-11-en-4 α -ol	2/24
93	n-Octyl butyrate	42
94	(2E, 4E)-Farnesol	2/14
95	14-Hydroxy- α -muurolole	2/3
96	6,10,14-Trimethyl-2-pentadecanone	2/30/5/6/16/27/29
97	Hexadecanoic acid	2/5/16/17/27/34
98	Isovaleric acid	3/30
99	α -Thujene	3/8/9/10/11/14/15/16/18/24/23/28/33/34/43
100	Borneol	3/8/10/11/16/18/19/24/25/27/28/33/36/37/40/14
101	Citronellol	3/14/16/19/23/33
102	Bornyl acetate	3/8/18/24/25/27/36/38/40/10

103	Myrtenyl acetate	3/8
104	α -Terpinyl acetate	3/14/31
105	Citronellyl acetate	3/14/18/23/33
106	α -Gurjunene	3/8/12/13/14/24/27/40
107	β -Gurjunene	3/24/31/40
108	<i>allo</i> -Aromadendrene	3/14/16/24/31/37/40
109	<i>Dehydro</i> -Aromadendrene	3/12/22
110	9- <i>epi</i> -(<i>E</i>)-Caryophyllene	3/8/34
111	β -Chamigrene	3/34
112	<i>cis</i> - β -Guaiene	3/16/31/39
113	Viridiflorene	3/8/22
114	β -Bisabolene	3/9/11/14/15/18/22/24/29/33/34/34/37/35/43
115	Kessane	3
116	Elemol	3/4/14/15/19/31/39
117	Guaiol	3/8/14/19/31
118	10- <i>epi</i> - γ -Eudesmol	3/8/22/31
119	Acetoxyvaleranone	3
120	<i>epi</i> - α -Cadinol	3/16/22/14/28/31/34
121	Hinesol	3/4
122	Valerenal	3
123	Valeranone	3
124	<i>epi</i> - α -Bisabolol	3
125	Valerenic acid	3
126	Pentanol	4/30
127	(2 <i>Z</i>)-Pentenol	4
128	<i>n</i> -Octyl isobutyrate	42
129	Pentacosane	17/6/14/16/27/29/34
130	Octyl adipate	6
131	4,8,12,16-Tetramethylheptadecan-4-olide	6
132	Tricosane	6/8/14/16/27/29
133	Neophytadiene	6/34
134	Stearic acid	6/14/30
135	Oleic acid	6/30
136	6-heptyltetrahydro-2H-pyran-2-one	6
137	Dihydro-5-tetradecyl-2(3H)-furanone	6
138	Heptadecanoic acid	6
139	(3 <i>E</i> ,5 <i>E</i>)-pseudoionone	6
140	Octadecanal	6/27
141	9-Hexadecenoic acid	6
142	Cyclohexadecanolide	6
143	Methyl hexadecanoate	6/30/34/5/27/14/17/29
144	Farnesylacetone	6/16/17/27/29
145	Nonadecane	6/14/15/29/30
146	5-methyl-5-pentyl-dihydro-2(3H)-furanone	6
147	Pentadecanoic acid	6/27/30
148	3-Heptadecanone	6
149	Hexadecanal	6/30/33
150	Octadecane	6/14/15/16/27/30
151	(2 <i>Z</i>)-pentadecenol	6
152	9-methylene-9H-fluorene	6

153	Hexanal	4/14/21/27/29
154	Ethyl acetate	4
155	Furfural	4/27/30
156	Pentanoic acid	4
157	(<i>E,Z</i>)-Farnesol	6/22
158	Furfuryl alcohol	4/30
159	(<i>E,E</i>)- α -Farnesene	14/19/34/40
160	2-Heptenone	4
161	Heptanal	4/27/30
162	2-Acetyl furan	4
163	Pentyl acetate	4
164	Methyl caproate	4
165	(<i>2E</i>)-Heptenal	4/27/30
166	Benzaldehyde	4/8/14/17/24/27/29/30/37
167	5-Methyl furfural	4/30/17/27
168	Heptanol	4/30
169	2-Propyl thiophene	4
170	3-Octanone	4/41
171	6-methyl-5-hepten-2-one	4/19/23/24/27/30
172	2-Pentylfuran	4/27/30
173	(<i>Z</i>)-Phytol	16
174	(<i>2E,4E</i>)-Heptadienal	4/27/29
175	2-(methoxymethyl)-3,5-dimethyl-2,5-cyclohexadien-1,4-dione	6
176	<i>exo</i> -2-Hydroxycineole	37
177	Benzeneacetaldehyde	6/4/17/27/29/34/37/16
178	γ -hexalactone	4
179	(<i>2E</i>)-Octenal	4/6/27/30
180	Vinyl caproate	4
181	<i>trans</i> -Linalool oxide	4/28/30/37
182	(<i>3E,5Z</i>)-Octadien-2-one	4
183	Hexanoic acid	4
184	5-formyl-2-pentylthiophene	6
185	(<i>3E,5E</i>)-Octadien-2-one	4
186	Linalool	4/8/14/15/19/24/25/27/28/30/31/32/33/35/37/38/39/40/43/7
187	Geraniol	4/14/19/28/33/37/38/5
188	(<i>2E,4E</i>)-Octadienal	4
189	Phenylethylalcohol	4/6/16/30
190	<i>trans-p</i> -Mentha-2,8-dien-1-ol	4/24/40
191	Pentadecanal	6/29/30
192	Heptanoic acid	4
193	Limona ketone	4
194	<i>cis-p</i> -Mentha-2,8-dien-1-ol	4/24
195	(<i>3E</i>)-Nonen-2-one	4
196	Camphor	4/8/10/12/14/16/18/19/25/27/28/33/40
197	(<i>E</i>)-5-ethyl-6-methyl-3-hepten-2-one	4
198	Lilac aldehyde	4
199	Isobutyl valerate	42
200	(<i>2E</i>)-Nonenal	4/27/30/34
201	<i>cis</i> -Linalyl oxide	4
202	Neryl acetate	14/23/33

203	Terpinen-4-ol	4/8/9/10/11/14/15/18/19/16/22/24/25/26/28/31/33/34/37/27/30/36/40/38/43/41
204	Menthol	4/5/14/23/27/16
205	Octanoic acid	4
206	<i>p</i> -Cymen-8-ol	4/13/16/32/33/37/43
207	Methyl salicylate	4/37
208	Dodecane	4/30
209	α -Cubebene	12/14/15/16/24/34/37/39/40
210	Octyl acetate	4/33/42
211	Decanoic acid	4/27
212	(2 <i>E</i> ,4 <i>E</i>)-Nonadienal	4/27/30
213	4-Methylene isophorone	4
214	Methyl pelargonate	4
215	<i>trans</i> -Carveol	4/8/24/37
216	Nerol	4/14
217	<i>cis</i> -Carveol	4/24/36
218	Carvone	4/5/24/27/7
219	γ -Octalactone	4
220	<i>p</i> -Anis aldehyde	4
221	(2 <i>E</i>)-Decenal	4/6/29/30
222	(<i>E</i>)-Cinnamaldehyde	4/14
223	Pelargonic acid	4/6/30
224	(<i>E</i>)-Anethole	4/20/27/7
225	Indole	4/6/16/17
226	2-Undecanone-(2 <i>E</i> ,4 <i>Z</i>)- decadienal	4
227	Ethyl hexanoate	24
228	Carvacrol	4/9/10/11/14/16/24/28/31/33/41
229	4-vinyl- <i>o</i> -guaiacol	4
230	Myrtenol	8/10/16/22/31
231	Eugenol	4/8/14/16/20/25/27
232	γ -Nonalactone	4/6/30
233	<i>Ent</i> -Spathulenol	27
234	Heptadecane	6/2/15/16/29/30
235	Methyl eugenol	4/22/25/27/7
236	Dihydroactinidiolide	6/30
237	Geranyl acetone	4/6/14/22/23/16/27/30
238	2-Dodecanone	4
239	Paeonol	4
240	γ -Decalactone	4
241	<i>ar</i> -curcumene	4/8/16/19/34/27
242	2-Pentadecanone	6/16/30
243	2-Tridecanone	4/16/29
244	α -Selinene	4/15/18/27/37/40/41/43/7
245	α -Calacorene	4/16/22/28/34
246	(2 <i>E</i>)-Tetradecenol	6
247	Humulene epoxide II	4/8/16/34/37
248	(2 <i>Z</i>)-Tetradecenol	6
249	Tridecylic acid	6/30
250	Hexahydrofarnesol	6
251	Tetradecanal	6/29/30/33
252	<i>ar</i> -turmerone	4
253	(3 <i>Z</i>)-butylidene phthalide	4
254	Cadalene	4/16
255	(<i>Z</i>)-ligustilide	4
256	Myristic acid	4/6/5/14/30
257	<i>n</i> -Octanol	30/37/42

258	<i>cis</i> -Linalool oxide	4/14/28/30/37
259	Methyl linoleate	4/6/29/30/27
260	Methyl oleate	4/14/30
261	Methyl phytol	4
262	Methyl stearate	4/14
263	Ethyl phytol	4
264	Linoleic acid	4/27/29/30
265	Heptacosane	4/6/16/27/34/6
266	Valerenol	3
267	β -Linalool	5
268	Myristicin	6/7/18/26/27/34
269	α -Bourbonene	5
270	α -Oplopanone	14
271	α -Chamigrene	5
272	Hexadecane	6/15/27/30
273	3-Eicosyne	5
274	<i>n</i> -Butyl butyrate	42
275	Isobutyl phthalate	5
276	3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol	5
277	<i>n</i> -Butyl isobutyrate	42
278	Isophytol	5
279	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester	5
280	9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester	5/27
281	<i>cis</i> -Piperitol	16
282	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid	5
283	9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol	5
284	Benzyl alcohol	6
285	5-ethenyldihydro-5-methyl-2(3H)-furanone	6/4
286	<i>p</i> -methyl-benzaldehyde	6
287	<i>o</i> -Guaiacol	6/30/27
288	2,6-dimethyl-cyclohexanol	6
289	Propanoic acid, butyl ester	42
290	Adamantol	6
291	Decanol	6
292	2,3-Dihydro-benzofuran	6
293	5-Methyl-1-heptene	6
294	β -Cyclocitral	6/29/30
295	2,7-dimethyl-1-octanol	6
296	3-ethyl-4-methyl-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione	6
297	Geranial	6/14/19/23/33/30
298	2-Undecanone	6/19
299	4-vinyl-guaiacol	6/16/30
300	(2 <i>E</i>)-undecenol	6
301	2,2-dimethyl-1-(2-hydroxy-1-methylethyl)propanoate	6
302	2-methyl-3-hydroxy-	6

	2,4,4-trimethylpentylpropanoate	
303	Megastigmatrienone	6/17
304	Isopropyl isovalerate	42
305	Vanillin	6
306	6,10-dimethyl-2-undecanone	6/30
307	Dodecanal	6/30/33
308	2,3-dimethyl-undecane	6
309	Undecylic acid	6
310	(<i>E</i>)-Nerolidol	6/14/16/24/15/19/37/40/7
311	5,6-epoxy- β -ionone	6
312	α -Patchoulene	24
313	(<i>Z</i>)-3-hexenal	21
314	<i>cis</i> -muurolo-3,5-diene	24/31/34/40
315	Isodihydrocarveol acetate	24
316	<i>trans-p</i> -menth-2-en-1-ol	8/16/37
317	Thymol methyl ether	22/28
318	Carvacrol methyl ether	11/28
319	<i>cis-p</i> -menth-2-en-1-ol	8/16/31/37
320	1-Tridecene	24
321	Carvacryl acetate	14
322	<i>trans</i> -Carvone oxide	24
323	Thymol	8/9/11/14/16/18/22/23/28/41/43
324	Safrole	7/32
325	β -Himachalene	24/34
326	Toluene	17
327	5- <i>tert</i> -Butyl-1,3-cyclopentadiene	17
328	Propyl butyrate	42
329	2-Ethyl-3,6-dimethylpyrazine	17
330	Benzyl nitrile	17
331	2,2,4-Trimethyl-pentadiol	17
332	2,3-Epoxy-carane	17
333	Tridecane	17/14/27/29/30
334	1,1,6-Trimethyl-1,2-dihydronaphthalene	17/27
335	2- <i>tert</i> -Butyl-1,4-dimethoxybenzene	17
336	(<i>E</i>)-6,10-dimethylundeca-5,9-dien-2-one	17
337	4,6-Dimethyl-dodecane	17
338	3,3,5,6-Tetramethyl-1-indanone	17
339	2,3,6-Trimethyl-naphthalene	17
340	1-[2,3,6-Trimethyl-phenyl]-2-butanone	17
341	1-[2,3,6-Trimethyl-phenyl]-3-buten-2-one	17
342	Isopropyl butyrate	42
343	Docosane	17/15/27/29
344	1-Docosene	17
345	Hexacosane	14/16/17/27/29

346	(<i>E</i>)- β -ocimene	14/15/23/14/24/22/26/28/30/27/33/34/37/38/40/41
347	<i>trans</i> -Sabinene hydrate	8/9/11/15/16/28/31/40
348	<i>cis</i> -Carvone oxide	24
349	<i>trans</i> -Verbenol	24
350	γ -Muurolene	11/16/19/24/26/28/37/40
351	Ledene	10/37
352	Carvenone	24
353	<i>trans</i> -Dihydrocarvone	24
354	<i>cis</i> -Dihydrocarvone	24/28
355	<i>p</i> -Mentha-1(7),5-dien-2-ol	24
356	(<i>Z,E</i>)- α -farnesene	24
357	Cedrol	7/27
358	β -Bisabolol	7
359	Apiole	7/18/26
360	β -Caryophyllene	5/8/9/10/11/12/13/14/15/18/20/24/16/22/23/25/26/32/35/38/40/36/27/33/34/37/39/28/41/43
361	τ -Muurolol	5/15/16/24/37/40
362	α -Isophoron	17/29
363	2,6,6-Trimethyl-2-cyclohexene-1,4-dione	17/6
364	α -Ionone	17/14
365	α -Ionene	17
366	β -Ionone	17/6/29/30/37/2/3/4/27
367	Ledene oxide	17
368	Isolongifolene	17/12
369	α -Methyl-benzene methanol	43
370	Croweacin	43
371	3-methyl-1-butanol	30
372	Pinocarvyl acetate	43
373	(<i>Z</i>)-3-hexenol	14/21/37
374	<i>n</i> -Hexyl octanoate	42
375	2-Heptanone	27/30
376	Yomogi alcohol	8
377	Artemisia ketone	8
378	Artemisia alcohol	8
379	Hotrienol	8
380	2-methyl butyl isovalerate	8
381	α -Campholenal	8/34/14
382	Veratrole	8
383	<i>trans</i> -Pinocarveol	8/16/24/31
384	Pinocarvone	8/16/24
385	δ -Terpineol	8
386	<i>cis</i> -Pinocamphone	8
387	Artemisyl acetate	8
388	Myrtenal	8/14/24/34
389	<i>trans</i> -Piperitol	8/14/31
390	<i>trans</i> -Myrtanol	8
391	<i>cis</i> -Chrysanthenyl acetate	8/24
392	Geranyl formate	8
393	<i>trans</i> -Pinocarvyl acetate	8/16
394	<i>trans</i> -Carvyl acetate	8/14/23/24
395	Cyclosativene	8/12/13/14/24/40

396	<i>cis</i> -Carvyl acetate	8/24
397	<i>trans</i> -Myrtnanol acetate	8
398	Italicene	8/34
399	<i>cis</i> -Muurolo-4(14),5-diene	8/31/34/40
400	γ -Curcumene	8/31/34
401	α -Zingiberene	8/19/34
402	β -Curcumene	8/34
403	<i>cis</i> -Dracunculifoliol	8
404	Palustrol	8/16
405	Viridiflorol	8/10/14/31/37
406	Isolongifolan-7- α -ol	8
407	1- <i>epi</i> -cubenol	8/16/24/37
408	Zingiberenol	8/19
409	3-Thujopsanone	8
410	α -Bisabolol	8/11/14/15/18/33/43
411	Methyl carvacrol	41
412	Chamazulene	8/27
413	Xanthorrhizol	8
414	Thymoquinone	9/28
415	<i>cis</i> -Salvene	10
416	<i>trans</i> -Salvene	10
417	Tricyclene	10/16/19/40/41
418	<i>o</i> -Cymene	10/34
419	<i>cis</i> -Ocimene	10/27
420	α -Terpinolene	10/14/27/1/8/11/12/15/18/19/24/31/32/33/34/37/38/40/41/43
421	β -Thujone	10/12/14/16/24
422	α -Thujone	10/16/24
423	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptan-3-one	10
424	Methyl thymol	41
425	Guaiene	35
426	Naphthalene	10/16/30
427	α -Guaiene	10/13/14/39
428	<i>trans</i> - β -Bergamotene	11
429	Thymohydroquinone	11/28
430	5-Methylenenorbornene	12
431	Santolina triene	12/27
432	Verbenene	12/14
433	Ethyl propanoate	12
434	1-Octene	12
435	α -Fenchene	12/38
436	<i>m</i> -Cymenene	12
437	<i>cis</i> - β -Terpineol	12/14
438	<i>neo</i> -3-thujanol	12
439	Citronellal	12/19/33
440	(<i>Z</i>)-Ocimenone	12
441	(<i>E</i>)-Ocimenone	12
442	Methyl citronellate	12/23
443	<i>neo</i> -3-thujyl acetate	12
444	Patchoulene	12
445	Cyperene	12/13
446	α -Cedrene	12/31/34
447	β -Cedrene	12/31
448	Selina-3,7-diene	12/13
449	<i>cis</i> -Sesquisabinene	12

	hydrate	
450	6,11-Oxidoacor-4-ene	12
451	α -Agarofuran	12/14
452	Geranyl- <i>n</i> -butyrate	12/14/28
453	Ledol	12/37/39
454	β -Caryophyllene alcohol	12/22
455	13-Norcypera- 1(5),11(12)-diene	13
456	Rotundene	13
457	Pentadec-1-ene	13
458	α -Bulnesene	13
459	Hexadecatriene	13
460	Heptadeca-1,8-diene	13
461	Aplotaxene	13
462	β -Santalene	13
463	1- <i>p</i> -Menthene	13
464	9,10-Dehydro isolongifolene	13
465	Acetophenone	14
466	α -Pinene oxide	14
467	<i>endo</i> -Fenchol	14/37
468	1-Octen-3-ol acetate	14/23
469	Caran-3 β -ol	38
470	Octan-3-ol acetate	14/23
471	(<i>E</i>)-Pinene hydrate	14
472	Muurola-4,10(14)-dien- 1 β -ol	37
473	Ipsdienol	14/41
474	11- α H-himachal-4-en-1- <i>beta</i> -ol	8
475	<i>ar</i> -turmerol	8
476	<i>p</i> -Methylacetophenone	14
477	<i>p</i> -Cymene-8-ol	14
478	Cryptone	14/15/19
479	Verbenone	14/22/24
480	Thymyl methyl ether	14
481	Pulegone	14/16/23/36
482	Cuminal	14/18/1/4/43
483	Myrtanol	14
484	Piperitone	14/16/26/36
485	Phenylethyl acetate	14
486	Nonanoic acid	14/5
487	Isobornyl acetate	14/23/24
488	Piperitenone	14/16/23/36
489	α -Longipinene	14
490	Thymyl acetate	14/22
491	Teferdine	34
492	Geranyl acetate	14/18/19/23/31/33/37/38/43
493	Linalyl butyrate	14
494	β -Copaene	14/15/28/31/34
495	γ -Elemene	14/18/43
496	Cinnamyl acetate	14
497	β -Humulene	14
498	γ -Humulene	14
499	Valencene	14/22/33/39
500	Bicyclogermacrene	14/22/24/26/31/33/34/35/37/39

501	β -Cadinene	14/24
502	<i>cis</i> -Calamenene	14/15/30/16/22/27
503	Zonarene	14/23
504	Caryophylla-4(12),8(13)-dien-5 β -ol	37
505	(<i>Z</i>)-Isoeugenol acetate	14
506	β -Calacorene	14/16
507	Germacrene-D-4-ol	14/27
508	2-Phenylethyl tiglate	14
509	<i>cis</i> -Isolongifolanone	14/39
510	α -Acorenol	14
511	Torreyol	14/15/37
512	Bulnesol	14
513	Juniper camphor	14
514	β -Sinensal	14
515	(<i>E,E</i>)-Farnesyl acetate	14
516	Caryophylla-4(14),8(15)-dien-5-ol	31/34
517	1-Eicosene	14
518	Manoyl oxide	14/23
519	Palmitoleic acid	14
520	Palmitic acid	14/29/30
521	Kaurene	14
522	Eicosane	14/15/16/27
523	Tetracosane	14/16/17/27/29
524	Tetradecane	15/27/29/30
525	10- <i>epi</i> - α -eudesmol	31
526	Cubebol	15/24/37
527	Heneicosane	15/16/27
528	3-Methylcyclohexanone	16
529	β -Atlantone	34
530	<i>cis</i> -Cadina-1(6),4-diene	34
531	1-Dodecene	16
532	γ -Gurjunene	16/39
533	Epizonarene	16/34
534	α -Cadinene	16/37/40
535	<i>trans</i> -Calamenene	16/24/28/31/34/37
536	Octacosane	16/27
537	Nonacosane	16/27/34
538	Triacotane	16
539	Hentriacontane	16
540	Dotriacontane	16
541	<i>p</i> -Menth-1-en-8-ol	17
542	2,6,6-trimethylcyclohexa-1,3-dienecarbaldehyde	17/27
543	<i>p</i> -Cresol	18/30
544	Cuminol	18
545	Cuminyl acetate	18/43
546	Germacrene A	18/31
547	<i>trans</i> - α -Bisabolene	18/33
548	Dillapiole	18/26/43
549	Isospathulenol	18/37
550	Nothoapiole	18
551	2-Heptanol	19/37
552	2-Nonanone	19/30/37

553	Neral	19/33/30
554	<i>Endo</i> -bornylacetate	19
555	δ -Selinene	19
556	Acorenone B	19
557	(<i>E,E</i>)-Farnesal	19
558	Chavicol	20
559	Nicotine	20
560	Coumarin	20
561	Eugenol acetate	20
562	(<i>Z</i>)- β -Santalene	33
563	(<i>E</i>)-3-Hexenal	21
564	(<i>Z</i>)-2-Hexenal	21
565	(<i>E</i>)-3-Hexen-1-ol	21/24
566	(<i>Z</i>)-2-Hexen-1-ol	21
567	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexen-1-ol	21
568	(<i>Z</i>)-4-Hexen-1-ol	21
569	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl formate	21
570	Hexyl acetate	21/42
571	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl acetate	21
572	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl acetate	21
573	Hexyl propionate	21
574	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl propionate	21
575	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl propionate	21
576	Hexyl butyrate	21/42
577	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl butyrate	21
578	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl butyrate	21
579	Hexyl isobutyrate	21/42
580	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl isobutyrate	21
581	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl 2-methylbutyrate	21
582	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl 2-methylbutyrate	21
583	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl 3-methylbutyrate	21
584	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl 3-methylbutyrate	21
585	Hexyl tiglate	21
586	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl tiglate	21
587	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl tiglate	21
588	Hexyl hexanoate	21/42
589	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl hexanoate	21
590	(<i>E</i>)-2-Hexenyl hexanoate	21
591	(<i>Z</i>)-3-Hexenyl benzoate	21
592	(<i>E</i>)-4-octene	22
593	<i>trans</i> -Pinocamphone	22
594	3,9-epoxy- <i>p</i> -menth-1-ene	22
595	Hydroxy citronellal	22
596	(<i>Z</i>)- β -damascenone	22
597	(<i>Z</i>)-ethyl cinnamate	22
598	7- <i>epi</i> -sesquithujene	22
599	<i>E</i> -amyl cinnamic alcohol	22
600	Farnesol (<i>Z,E</i>)	22
601	Isopulegone	23
602	<i>cis</i> -Piperitone epoxide	23
603	Piperitenone epoxide	23

604	Isopentyl acetate	24
605	S-ethyl pentanethioate	24
606	Thuja-2,4(10)-diene	24
607	Curzerene	40
608	(E)-3-hexenol acetate	24
609	3-methylbutyl butanoate	24
610	3-methylbutyl-2-methylpropanoate	24
611	1,4-Cineole	24
612	Butyl-2-methylbutanoate	24/42
613	<i>p</i> -Cymenene	24
614	Isoamyl-2-methylbutyrate	24
615	Chrysanthenone	24
616	<i>trans</i> -Sabinol	24
617	<i>cis</i> -Verbenol	24
618	Sabinaketone	24
619	Isopinocampone	24
620	α -Thujenal	24
621	Dihydro- <i>ar</i> -turmerone	12/39
622	<i>trans</i> -Muurolo-4(14),5-diene	19/31
623	<i>trans</i> -Sesquisabinene hydrate	19
624	Linalyl acetate	25/31
625	4-methoxycinnamaldehyde	25
626	Pentadecane	26/27/29/30
627	<i>cis</i> -1,3-Dimethylcyclohexane	27
628	<i>trans</i> -1,4-Dimethylcyclohexane	27
629	Octane	27
630	<i>cis</i> -1,4-Dimethylcyclohexane	27
631	Ethylcyclohexane	27
632	2,6-Dimethyl-1,5-heptadiene	27
633	1,2,5,5-Tetramethyl-1,3-cyclopentadiene	27
634	(Z)-4-Heptenal	27
635	<i>trans</i> -cadina-1(6),4-diene	8/19/31/40/14/24/27/30
636	1,2,3-Trimethylbenzene	27
637	<i>trans</i> -2-(2-Pentenyl)furan	27
638	3-Ethyl-2-methyl-1,3-hexadiene	27
639	3,5-Octadien-2-ol	27
640	<i>trans</i> -muurolo-3,5-diene	31
641	<i>trans</i> -2-Methyldecalin	27
642	1,3,8- <i>p</i> -Menthatriene	27/24
643	2,2,4-Trimethyl-3-cyclohexene-1-carbaldehyde	27
644	6,6-Dimethyl-2-methylene-bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-3-	27

	one	
645	<i>p</i> -Mentha-1,5-dien-8-ol	27/34
646	<i>p</i> -Ethylguaiaicol	27
647	5-(2-Propenyl)-1,3-benzodioxole	27
648	<i>trans</i> -Carveyl acetate	27
649	<i>cis</i> -Jasmone	27/40/37
650	(<i>E</i>)-Isoeugenol	27
651	3-Methyltetradecane	27
652	Tetradecanoic acid	27
653	Phenanthrene	27
654	Phthalic acid, diisobutyl ester	27
655	Dehydroelsholtzia ketone	12
656	(<i>Z,Z,Z</i>)-9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid	27/30
657	3-Octanol	28
658	Nonanol	28/30
659	<i>trans-p</i> -2-Menthen-1-ol	28
660	Thymol formate	28
661	Borneol propionate	28
662	2-Methoxy-4-ethyl-6-methylphenol	28
663	(<i>2E,4Z</i>)-Heptadienal_	29
664	Benzofurane	29
665	β -Patchoulene	27
666	<i>allo</i> -Ocimene	29/34
667	(<i>2E,6Z</i>)- Nonadienal	29
668	Tetradecene	29
669	Farnesane	29
670	Methyl linolenate	29
671	Ethyl linolenate	29
672	<i>n</i> -Butanol	30
673	2-Hexanone	30
674	3-Hexanol	30
675	3-Hexanone	30
676	2-Hexanol	30
677	2-Methylpyridine	30
678	Valericacid	30
679	2-acetyl-1-pyrroline	30
680	Phenol	30
681	Caproic acid	30
682	2,3-Octanedione	30
683	2-Octanone	30
684	1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	30/24
685	1,4-Dichlorobenzene	30
686	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	30
687	3-Octen-2-one	30
688	<i>o</i> -Cresol	30
689	2-Acetylpyrrole	30
690	Enantic acid	30
691	3,5-Octadien-2-one	30
692	6-methyl-3,5-heptadien-2-one	30
693	Terpinen-4-ol acetate	31/38
694	1-(3-methylphenyl)-	30

	ethanone	
695	3,5-Xylenol	30
696	<i>p</i> -Menthan-3-one	30/4/14/16/23/27/36/14/16/23
697	Benzoic acid	30
698	Caprylic acid	30
699	4-Vinylphenol	30
700	2-Decanone	30
701	2-Hydroxy-6-methylbenzaldehyde	30
702	Benzothiazole	30
703	2-Methylnaphthalene	30
704	(2 <i>E</i> ,4 <i>Z</i>)-decadienal	30
705	<i>n</i> -Undecanal	30/33
706	1-Methylnaphthalene	30
707	τ -Cadinol	37/40
708	Caryophyllene alcohol	40
709	(2 <i>E</i>)-undecenal	30
710	Patchouli alcohol	39
711	Capric acid	30
712	Biphenyl	30
713	1,3-Dimethylnaphthalene	30
714	Tridecanal	30
715	Lauric acid	30
716	Methyl tetradecanoate	30
717	Ethyl tetradecanoate	30
718	Isoterpinolene	40
719	2-Heptadecanone	30
720	Ethyl hexadecanoate	30/34
721	Santalol	38
722	Estragole	25
723	Cyclocolorenone	37
724	Khusinol	37
725	(<i>E</i>)-Asarone	39
726	Longifolene	30/40
727	Isopulegol	31
728	Thuj-3-en-10-al	31
729	Geranyl butanoate	31
730	<i>trans</i> -Sabinyl acetate	31
731	α -Himachalene	31
732	α -Muurolol	31
733	2-Isopropenyl-5-methyl-4-hexenylacetate	27
734	<i>neo</i> -isopulegol	31
735	2,3-Dehydro-1,8-cineole	27
736	Epi-bicyclosesquiphellandrene	27
737	γ -Selinene	27
738	Isodihydrocarveol	37
739	Cuparene	27/34
740	2,4-Dimethylether-phloroacetophenone	37
741	(<i>Z</i>)- β -damascone	31
742	(<i>Z</i>)-caryophyllene	31
743	Carquejyl acetate	22
744	β -Copaen-4- α -ol	14/22/24/37

745	7-epi- α -selinene	12/19
746	α -Caryophyllene	32/35
747	Decane	33
748	<i>cis</i> -Limonene oxide	33
749	<i>trans</i> -Limonene oxide	33
750	Perilla aldehyde	33
751	Dihydrolinalyl acetate	33
752	α - <i>cis</i> -Bergamotene	33
753	Norbornanol	33
754	Campherenol	33
755	Nootkatone	33
756	Sylvestrene	34/39/40
757	<i>p</i> -Mentha-2,4(8)-diene	34
758	6-Camphenone	34
759	Perillene	34
760	Isoledene	34/39
761	Daucene	34
762	β -Barbatene	34
763	β -Acoradiene	34/39
764	Isodaucene	34
765	γ -Cuprenene	34
766	α -Copaen-11-ol	34
767	Elemicin	34/37/39
768	(<i>E</i>)- α -Isomethyl-ionol acetate	34
769	Eudesma-4(15),7-dien- 1 β -ol	34/37
770	Ethyl linoleate	34
771	<i>m</i> -Ethyl cumene	36
772	Junenol	37
773	Isophorene	36
774	1-Phenyl-1,4-butanediol	36
775	(<i>E,E</i>)-Hexa-2,4-dienal	37
776	(<i>E</i>)-Hept-2-en-1-ol	37
777	3-Phenylpropanol	37
778	Perilla alcohol	37
779	Methyl anisate	37
780	1,3,5-Trimethoxybenzene	37
781	Methyl-(<i>Z</i>)-isoeugenol	37
782	(<i>E</i>)-Methylisoeugenol	37/39
783	Tetradecan-1-ol	37
784	(<i>E</i>)-Nerolidol acetate	37
785	Ethyl hydroquinone	39
786	(<i>Z</i>)-Nerolidol	39
787	Salvial-4(14)-en-1-one	34
788	Camphene hydrate	37
789	Oplopanone	37
790	Seychellene	39
791	(<i>Z</i>)-Asarone	39

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